

ELECTRODE PROPERTIES OF OXY-GRAPHENE/PAN-BASED CARBON NANOFIBER COMPOSITES FOR SUPERCAPACITOR

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1. Introduction

Now the prospect of supercapacitors with high power density extends their application to various other novel devices such as load-levellers, hybrid capacitor-battery systems, cold-starting assistants. Their double-layer capacitances strongly depend on the types and forms of the electrode materials. Various forms and textures of porous carbons have been examined as possible electrode materials for supercapacitors [1-3]. Among them, 1D carbon nanotubes have attracted a lot of attention because they have large accessible surface areas and relatively high electrical conductivities, which make them very promising as efficient electrode materials for high-power supercapacitors [4-6]. Currently, intrinsic problems, such as their limited available amount of charge and high cost, combined with their low effective specific surface areas, limit the practical usage of carbon nanotubes as the electrode material in supercapacitors. Recently, graphene has been discovered for its outstanding electronic, thermal, and mechanical properties for different applications like energy storage devices [7-10]. The properties of the graphenes are suitable for the electrodes of electrochemical energy storage devices due to their super characteristics: chemical stability, low mass density, low resistivity, and large surface area. A supercapacitor is a crucial device in energy storage/conversion system because it is applied to various areas such as electric vehicles, uninterrupted power supplies [11].

In order to apply the supercapacitors to various practical devices, such as electric vehicles, the

development of supercapacitors with both high power and high energy densities is required. Therefore, this work proposes a method to prepare electrodes for supercapacitor with graphene embedded in polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon nanofiber (CNF) composite by electrospinning method, followed by stabilization and carbonization. The properties of the graphene/PAN based carbon nanofiber composites were prepared and characterized by SEM, TEM, TGA and Raman measurements. The electrochemical properties were also evaluated by cyclic voltammetry(CV), charge-discharge, and ac impedance.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation of Graphene/PAN based CNFs

The oxy-graphenes (OG) were sonicated for 1 h in dimethylformamide(DMF) solvent to disperse the OG before mixing with PAN solution. The dispersed OG was homogeneously mixed in a PAN solution to be 1, 3, 5, 10 and 20 wt%. The solutions were spun into fiber webs through a positively charged capillary using an electrospinning apparatus (NTPS-35K, NTSEE Co., Korea). The electrospun nanocomposite webs were stabilized in an air atmosphere at 280 °C and followed by carbonization at 1000 °C under an inert argon atmosphere to be carbon nano-fiber composites (CNFCs). The samples were identified as G-1, G-3, G-5, G-10 and G-20, indicating concentrations of 1, 3, 5, 10, and 20% of OG to PAN, respectively. To develop the porous structure of CNF, the stabilized fiber webs were heated at a rate of 5 °C/min up 800 °C and

activated for 1 hr by supplying 30 vol.% of steam in a carrier gas of N₂. The activated CNFCs were labelled G-Ac-1, G-Ac-3, G-Ac-5, G-Ac-10 and G-Ac-20, respectively.

2.2. Characterization

The morphology and size distribution of the composites were characterized using an FE-SEM (Hitachi, S-4700, Japan). The transmission electron micrographs (TEM) were taken model JEOL JEM-2010 FEF operating at 200 kV. TGA was carried out using a Shimadzu TGA 50 to determine the oxidation behaviors during heating at 10 °C /min up to 1000 °C in air. Specific surface areas were analyzed by the BET method using an ASPS 2020 Physisorption Analyzer (Micromeritics, USA). Backscattering Raman measurements were carried out with a Renishaw in Via-Reflex at room temperature. Supercapacitor cells were built by assembling two 2.25 cm² silica/carbon NFC electrodes separated by a filter paper in a 6 M KOH aqueous solution.

The electrochemical properties were determined with a galvanostatically measured with a WBCS3000 battery cycler system (WonA Tech Co., Korea) in aqueous 6 M KOH, and in 1.5 M tetraethylammonium tetrafluoroborate (TEABF₄) dissolved in acetonitrile (AC). In the case of the aqueous electrolytes, the cells were charged up to 1.0 V and. In organic electrolyte, the cells were charged up to 2.5 V and the specific discharge capacitance was measured in a wide range of current densities from 1 to 20 mA/cm². Cyclic voltammetry (CV) of the unit cell was performed in the potential range of 0-1 V at a scan rate of 25 mVs⁻¹. The ac impedance measurements were performed in the frequency range of 100 kHz to 100 MHz using an electrochemical impedance analyzer (Jahner Elektrik IM6, Germany).

3. Results and discussion

Fig. 1 shows SEM images of the CNFCs obtained with different OG concentrations after stabilization and carbonization. The results show that pure PAN based CNFs have relatively straight and smooth surfaces with diameter of 200 to 300 nm (Fig. 1(a)). The higher the concentration of OG, the more irregularity appeared and the more OG came out to surface as shown Fig. 1 (b-f). Fig. 1 (g-i) shows an example of the aggregated OGs embedded

in the CNFs, when OGs were not well dispersed at 20 wt% of OGs concentration.

Fig. 1. SEM images of the OG containing PAN based CNF at various graphene concentrations (a) 0, (b) 1, (c) 3, (d) 5, (e) 10, (f) 20 wt%; TEM image (g) 3, (h) 5, (i) 20 wt%

Raman spectra provide information on the crystallinity of the graphite-based materials. In Fig. 2(a), there are three main bands around 1360, 1600 and 2700 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the breathing mode of k-point phonons of A_{1g} symmetry (D band), the first-order scattering of the E_{2g} phonons (G band) and the second order of the D band (2D) of graphene, respectively [12].

Fig.2. Raman spectra of CNFCs as a function of OG concentration, (b) The intensity ratio (R) for CNFCs and crystalline domain size (L_d)

It is well known that R-value, the intensity ratio of the D-band to the G-band, is also sensitive to the ratio of concentration of graphite edge planes and/or crystal boundaries to standard graphite planes. The

R-values (I_D/I_G) decreased, which is strongly indicating the transformation of disordered carbons into graphitic carbons with increasing OG concentration (Fig. 2(b)). The sample crystallinity can be quantified by an empirical formula, where the crystallite domain size L_a (nm) of graphite is obtained by $L_a = 4.35/R$ [13]. Using this equation, L_a was enhanced from 4.25 to 4.55 nm with increasing OG concentration, as shown in Fig. 2(b).

Fig. 3(a) presents the TGA curves of a pristine sample and of CNFCs containing oxy-graphene in N_2 flow. In almost all cases, the amount of the residue retained above 800 °C increased with an increase in the concentration of oxy-graphene. The specific surface area was maximum at 1% OG and decreased with further increase in OG concentration. The electrical conductivity of the oxy-graphene containing CNFs increased up to 5% of OG but decreased at G20, which would come from the reduced contact area among the individual fibers due to the rough surface at 20% OG as shown in Fig. 1 (i). In general, the CNFC with high concentration oxy-graphene showed higher electrical conductivity than pure CNF, due to the nature of the graphene.

Fig. 3. (a) TGA thermograms, (b) Pore characteristics and electrical conductivity for the CNFCs

The power density of the oxy-graphene containing CNFC web has been investigated by galvanostatic charge/discharge cycling at different current rate in the KOH aqueous electrolytes (Fig. 4a). Typical charge-discharge curves of web electrodes solution were determined at a constant current density of 1 mA/cm². The capacitance gradually decreased with increases in the discharge current density. The G-3 CNF web electrode had a greater specific capacitance at all current densities

than the other electrodes, which is attributed to the higher electrical conductivity (11.96 S cm⁻¹) and homogeneous distribution of OG in nanofiber matrix. Fig. 2 (b) shows a Ragone plot of the CNFC electrodes. The G-3 CNFC web electrode exhibited best performance with energy density of 14.0-19.0 Wh/kg at the respective power density of 400-30,000 W/kg, comparing with the performance of the pristine showing the energy density of 2.0-6.0 Wh/kg at the same range of power density. Cyclic voltammograms obtained at a scan rate of 25 mV/s are presented in Fig. 4c. As shown in the figure, G-3 presented a larger induced current than that of the other samples. In electrochemical impedance behavior of CNFC webs (Fig. 4d), the small arcs at high frequencies (see inset in Fig. 4d) indicate that the charge-transfer resistance between the electrode and the electrolyte was small, because the pore size of the carbon material was matched well with the size of the electrolyte. Furthermore, the steep linear slopes at low frequencies indicate that the kinetics of ion diffusion in solution, and the adsorption of ions onto the electrode surface were rapid.

Fig. 4. (a) Specific capacitances as a function of a various current densities, (b) Ragone plots for oxy-graphene/PAN based CNF at various oxy-graphene concentrations, (c) CV of the CNFC at a scan rate of 25 mV/s. (b) Complex-plane impedance plots of CNFC electrodes with a perturbation amplitude of 10 mV in KOH aqueous electrolytes

Presently, the electrical double-layer capacitors (EDLC) using activated carbon electrodes in organic electrolyte are mostly available on the market. The

reasons of this choice are the high specific surface area of activated carbons and the high attainable voltage in organic electrolyte. The physical activation using steam results in a more development of porosity within the CNFs. In the process of activation, the addition of oxy-graphene has significant influence on the fiber surface roughness. Fig. 5a~e show SEM images of activated CNFC webs with various OG contents. The G-Ac webs became curlier and more corrugated with increasing oxy-graphene concentrations. This is closely related to the morphology of OGs embedded in CNFs in Fig. 5 a and b. Some oxy-graphenes were aggregated and even exposed to the outer surface of nanofibers, when the OG was not well dispersed over 5 wt% of OG concentration, as shown in Fig. 5 c~e. Fig. 5f shows the adsorption equilibrium data of N₂ on activated carbon fibers that were also found to be Type I according to the IUPAC classification, indicating that the degree of microporosity was high. As the OG content increased, a slightly decrease in the nitrogen adsorption capacity and BET surface area (860-1100 m²/g) was observed.

Fig. 5. SEM images (a) G-Ac-1, (b) G-Ac-3, (c) G-Ac-5, (d) G-Ac-10, (e) G-Ac-20, (f) N₂ adsorption of the G-Ac at various OG concentrations

The power density of the activated OG containing CNF electrodes was investigated by galvanostatic charge/discharge cycling at different current rates in organic electrolyte (Fig. 6a). The G-Ac-3 web electrode showed highest specific capacitance at all current densities, which was attributed to the more homogeneous distribution of graphene in the CNF. The specific capacitance dependence on the current

rate was minimum for the sample of G-Ac-3. It is noteworthy that the capacitance remained above 70 F/g even at a discharge current of 20 mA/cm². The Ragone plot also shows that a high power density can be extracted without a significant degradation in the energy density (Fig. 6b). Efficient energy storage devices were produced using the G-Ac-3 electrode, and energy densities of 60-77 Wh/kg and power densities of 400-30,000 W/kg were obtained.

Fig. 6. (a) Specific capacitances as a function of a various current densities, (b) Ragone plots for activated CNFC webs at various OG concentrations in organic electrolyte

3.3 Conclusions

PAN solutions dispersed with 1-20 wt% OG were electrospun into composited fibers and followed by stabilization, carbonization/activation to be used as electrodes for EDLC. The electrospinning was successfully performed with homogeneous dispersions of the OG in the 100-300nm size after carbonization/activation. The electrodes of the EDLC improved not only in the specific capacitance but also in the energy density; from the highest specific capacitance of 150 F/g and energy density of 19 Wh/kg in aqueous solution, while the performance in organic electrolyte showed the highest energy density of 77 Wh/kg at the same range of power density. The performance enhancements would be introduced from the increases in electrical conductivities and porosity of the hard carbon/OG composite fibers. The high power stability obtained in both electrolytic media is ascribed to the structural/textural advantage of the OG containing PAN based nanofibers. They combine (i) opened pores which enhance ions diffusion to the active surface; (ii) a high electrical conductivity which makes the interfacial charge

transfers easier. These materials present a new route for developing high power supercapacitors.

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